

PREPARING FOR RAINFALL NOWCASTING IN THE GOES-R ERA USING SEVIRI AND POLAR-ORBITING MICROWAVE DATA OVER AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The Advanced Baseline Imager (ABI) onboard the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES)-R platform will offer enhanced capabilities for satellite-based rainfall estimation and nowcasting over the current-generation GOES. The development of a rainfall nowcasting algorithm for GOES-R has relied extensively on proxy data from the Spinning Enhanced Infrared Visible Imager (SEVIRI) over Europe and Africa, since its 11 spectral bands are similar to bands that will be available on GOES-R. This rainfall nowcasting framework starts with estimates of current rain rate derived from visible and infrared data using an algorithm calibrated against rain rates from polar-orbiting microwave sensors. This current rain rate estimate and its immediate predecessor are analyzed using a K-Means feature detection technique to determine the motion of the identified precipitation features, and these motions are extrapolated forward in time to produce nowcasts of both accumulated 0-3 h future rainfall and the probability of measurable rainfall during the same time period. This paper describes the development of this algorithm framework.

Index Terms— *Satellite applications, Rain, Forecasting*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites-Series R (GOES-R) is scheduled to begin deployment in 2015 and to offer a significant improvement in capability over the current generation GOES instruments. For instance, the Advanced Baseline Imager (ABI) will offer 16 spectral bands, spatial resolution of 0.5 to 2 km, and full-disk scanning every 5 minutes, compared to the current Imager capabilities of 5 spectral bands, 1-4 km spatial resolution, and 30 min required for a full-disk scan [1]. GOES-R will also offer a Lightning Mapper (GLM) and improved space weather measurement capability.

The GOES-R Algorithm Working Group (AWG) has been tasked with providing recommended, demonstrated, and validated algorithms for processing GOES-R

observations into user-required products which satisfy requirements. The AWG is supported by 17 Algorithm Teams (AT)'s, including the Hydrology AT which is responsible for developing algorithms for rainfall rate, 0-3 hour rainfall potential, and 0-3 hour probability of rainfall.

2. ALGORITHM SELECTION PROCESS

Twelve potential candidate algorithms for retrieving current rainfall rate and nowcasting future rainfall (six each) were considered and tested for implementation in GOES-R. Three candidate rainfall algorithms were variants of the CPC MORPHing (CMORPH) [2] algorithm: QMPRPH, CPC-IRFREQ [3], and CMORPHIR; the others were the Naval Research laboratory (NRL) Blended algorithm [4], Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks (PERSIANN) [5], and the Self-Calibrating Multivariate Precipitation Retrieval (SCaMPR) [6]. Two of the nowcasting algorithms were variants of the Hydro-Nowcaster [7], while the others were the K-Means technique [8], two versions of Thunderstorm Initiation, Tracking, and Nowcasting (TITAN) [9], and the McGill Algorithm for Precipitation Nowcasting by Lagrangian Extrapolation (MAPLE) [10]. It should be noted that because the rain rate algorithm had not yet been selected, and because some algorithms had their own built-in algorithm for retrieving rainfall rates from satellite data, the algorithms were tested for their skill at predicting the time evolution of brightness temperature or reflectance from selected imager bands.

Data from the Spinning Enhanced Infrared Visible Imager (SEVIRI) onboard the METEOSAT-8 satellite was used as a proxy for the ABI since it has bands that are similar to 11 of the 16 ABI spectral bands and provides similar spatial (3 km) and temporal (15 min) resolution relative to polar-orbiting satellites like the MODerate resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS). Each of the algorithm developers was provided with 15-minute full-disk SEVIRI data for the 1st-5th of January, April, July, and October 2005, along with validation data from daily and hourly rain gauges and from the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) Precipitation Radar (PR) [11]. Since each of the six

candidate rainfall rate algorithms also used microwave (MW)-based rainfall rates as input, an 8-km resolution blended MW rainfall product using Special Sensor Microwave/Imager (SSM/I) [12], Advanced Microwave Sounding Unit (AMSU) / Microwave Humidity Sounder (MHS) [13], and TRMM Microwave Imager (TMI)-retrieved rain rates [14] was obtained from the product developer and provided to the rainfall rate algorithm developers.

In the second stage of the selection process, the algorithm developers were provided with 15-minute full disk SEVIRI data and corresponding MW rainfall rates for the 6th-9th of each of the 4 months and produced independent rain rate estimates or nowcasts of brightness temperature which were delivered to the AT for evaluation.

3. RAIN RATE ESTIMATION ALGORITHM

After a comparison of the six candidate rainfall rate algorithms, a version of the Self-Calibrating Multivariate Precipitation Retrieval (SCaMPR) [6] was selected. This version of SCaMPR had been modified to use 10 of the 11 SEVIRI bands instead of the three GOES Imager bands that are used in the current real-time version.

In brief, the overarching goal of SCaMPR is to use continuously available visible and infrared (IR) data to produce an accurate estimate of MW rain rates that are available continuously instead of only when MW overpasses are available. SCaMPR trains GOES-derived data against MW-derived rainfall estimates for two separate steps: identifying raining pixels and assigning rainfall rates to those pixels. Discriminant analysis is used to determine which GOES predictor(s) have the highest skill at discriminating raining from nonraining pixels and to compute the best calibration relationship for discrimination. Stepwise forward multiple linear regression is used to select the GOES predictor(s) with the highest skill at estimating rainfall rate and the coefficients associated with those predictors. SCaMPR includes nonlinear transformations of the rainfall rate predictors and updates its calibration whenever new MW rain rates become available.

More details on the current version of SCaMPR being run over North America can be found in [6]. The modifications for the GOES-R version include an expanded selection of channels and brightness temperature differences (BTD's) or inter-band reflectance differences in the predictor set to a total of 52 predictors (including nonlinear transformations); separate calibrations for each 30-degree latitude band; and the use of selected BTD's for classifying rainfall types in order to permit a calibration that is more tailored to each type. Specifically, the BTD's between the 7.34 μm and

11.2 μm bands (which is typically indicative of deep convection

Figure 1. Rainfall totals for the 24 hours ending 0600 UTC 7 April 2007 from SCaMPR (field) and rain gauges (circles).

when the brightness temperature is lower at 7.34 μm than at 11.2 μm and between 8.5 μm and 11.2 μm (lower brightness temperatures at 8.5 μm than at 11.2 μm typically indicate water clouds, while the opposite indicates ice-topped clouds) are used to classify precipitating clouds into cold-top convective, water-top, and ice-top. For illustration, Figure 1 shows a rainfall total over Africa for the 24 hours ending 0600 UTC 7 April 2005, with the gauge point values overlaid over the SCaMPR field.

4. RAINFALL NOWCASTING ALGORITHM

The comparison of the six candidate rainfall nowcasting algorithms led to the selection of the K-Means algorithm [8]. The algorithm identifies features in the rainfall (or cloud) fields using a K-Means segmentation technique that both identifies features and clusters similar nearby features together. The motion of each cluster is determined by overlaying the cluster from the current image onto the previous image and determining the direction of motion that minimizes the difference between the two images. After interpolating the resulting motion field onto a grid, these gridded motion vectors are used to extrapolate the position of each feature forward in time in 15-minute increments out

to 3 hours lead time. The feature identification and motion extrapolation are performed at 3 different spatial scales and

Figure 2. Rainfall nowcast totals for the 24 hours ending 0600 UTC 7 April 2007 from the K-Means algorithm (field) and rain gauges (circles). Note that this is a series of consecutive 3-hour nowcasts that has been created for illustration in order to compare to 24-hour rain gauges.

the results are combined to produce the final result. However, at each individual scale no changes are made to the size, shape, or intensity of each feature, since initial development of the K-Means algorithm was unable to produce a growth / decay adjustment that had a positive impact on the forecast. Possible adjustments based on the convective life cycle are currently under development for possible incorporation into the algorithm. For illustration, Figure 2 shows the sum of the 8 3-hour rainfall nowcasts for the 24 hours ending 0600 UTC 7 April 2005, with the gauge point values overlaid over the total rainfall potential field.

6. FUTURE WORK

The rainfall rate algorithm is on track for delivery of the 80% version of the algorithm code (meeting the requirements for code format, documentation, and speed, and able to meet at least 80% of the stated performance requirements) in September 2009; the 100% delivery is due 12 months later. The accuracy performance requirement is

that the average value of SCaMPR must be within 6.0 mm/h of the observed value, while the precision performance requirement is that, at a rain rate of 10 mm/h, 68% of the retrieved rain rates must be within 9.0 mm/h of the observed value. While these may appear not to be very strict requirements, it must be kept in mind that these are for validation of instantaneous rainfall rates at 2-km resolution—slight errors in the timing and/or location of precipitation will induce large errors at these scales that would be much less prominent over larger space or time scales.

The rainfall potential algorithm is on track for delivery of the 80% version of the algorithm code in August 2010; the 100% delivery is due 12 months later. The accuracy performance requirement is that the average value of the 3-hour nowcasts of rainfall accumulation must be within 5.0 mm/h of the observed value, 68% of the SCaMPR rain rates must be within 5.0 mm of the observed value. Note again that these requirements appear to be more stringent than for the rainfall rates because they represent 3-hour totals whereby many of the errors in instantaneous rates would cancel each other out.

Several projects with various collaborators are underway to improve the rainfall estimates and nowcasts. They include the aforementioned efforts to incorporate convective cycle information into the algorithms to allow more accurate prediction of time changes in rainfall rates; an orographic adjustment to the rainfall rates in complex terrain; Lagrangian (cloud-following) time changes in cloud properties; and the incorporation of cloud microphysical properties derived from ABI data into the rainfall rate algorithm. Correction for sub-cloud evaporation of hydrometeors in dry environments similar to what is used in the current operational Hydro-Estimator algorithm [15] is also under consideration. Though most of these improvements focus on the rainfall rate estimation, they are also anticipated to have a positive impact on the rainfall nowcasts since the estimates form their basis.

10. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS AND DISCLAIMER

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